

VISS

D7.2 Public Engagement Strategy

WP7, T7.3

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1 Executive Summary

This document constitutes the deliverable 7.2 *Public Engagement Strategy* and is a summary of activities to be performed by the ViSS project within task 7.3 *Public engagement*, representing its main result. This activity is framed within ViSS WP7 *ViSS outreach: Communication, dissemination, exploitation and capacity building* and therefore, the engagement activities complement the ViSS Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy (D7.1).

This is a **living document** which will be updated on M18 (D7.4; February 2025); on M33 (D7.9; May 2026), and on M48 (D7.15 *Final public engagement actions*; August 2027). The lessons learnt during the public engagement activities will be applied in other activities such as T7.4 (Networking and Clustering) and T7.5 (Open Innovation and capacity building).

The objective of the public engagement strategy in ViSS is to: **involve the relevant stakeholders** to participate in the SRL assessment in WP6 (T6.4), to **enhance the acceptability of ViSS results and solutions, support the social change processes** and to **increase awareness**, and communication & dissemination activities.

Therefore, **the aim of D7.2 is to design the conceptual framework for public engagement** (section 2) while actions related to public engagement are included in D7.4.

As a first step, an **ecosystem analysis** will be performed, considering the existing infrastructures for public engagement and the relevant stakeholders for the ViSS project at the regional level (section 3)

Subsequently, a **diagnosis** is performed in section 4, providing recommendations and selecting the most suitable resources to be used in the citizen engagement foreseen in ViSS. Furthermore, an **action plan** (section 5) is briefly drafted with priorities and activities to be deployed along the project. The main results will be further developed in future versions of this deliverable.

Finally, some **dissemination and communication measures** are defined in Section 6. These will be refined in the following periods, in coordination with the overall outreach activities planned in Task 7.2.

2 Introduction: Public Engagement processes

Public engagement describes the myriad of ways in which the activity and benefits of higher education and research can be shared with the public. Engagement is by definition a two-way process, involving interaction and listening, with the goal of generating mutual benefit (National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement (NCCP), 2014). The concept is considered a synonym for public participation and/or citizen engagement and both terms will be used throughout the document.

ViSS public engagement strategy relies on the **Quintuple Helix of Stakeholders** model (Carayannis et al., 2012), depicted in Figure 1 for the public participation. It is understood as collaborative knowledge generation involving relevant stakeholders for participating in the definition of the Safe and Sustainable by Design Framework (SSbD) and the SRL assessment that will take place in WP6, but it also plays a key role enhancing acceptability of the ViSS products, solutions and value chain and supporting the social change processes and increasing awareness required for the transition towards a circular economy, thus supporting the dissemination and communication strategy.

Figure 1 Quintuple helix model

Gender equality will be ensured along the project, according to RRI principles explained in VISS Ethics Handbook (D8.3). Gender equality will be promoted by addressing the diversity of gender representation for the participation in research activities, taking into consideration an intersectional approach, to increase representation in management and decision-making processes and reduce gender segregation. Moreover, **gender aspects will be integrated in the content of research and innovation**, ensuring the representation of different needs and points of view and interests are adequately addressed. This will entail including gender diversity in the sampling, recruitment of stakeholders, data analysis (including gender balance as quantitative variable) and evaluation (assessing different perceptions on sustainability and socioeconomic impacts across the SDGs, particularly SDG 5, SDG 11 and SDG12).

For further understanding of this document, several activities and deliverables related to the public engagement strategy should be considered:

- The ViSS project Description of the Action (DoA) part A which is Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement number 101081931 and contains the details of how the action (project) will be carried out. This document was prepared during the initiating and planning phase of the project.
- Under WP6, the SSbD and social readiness evaluation framework construction (T6.2) will implement participative methodologies to create the ViSS evaluation matrix (D6.3), considering regulations on food packaging (TCA), those related to safety for human health and the environment (IDE, UA), and assessment of social readiness (SRL) in terms of acceptance of end-users & consumers (KVC). The data collected and the instruments used for the evaluation in T6.4 will feed the Evaluation & Decision tool in T6.1.2.
- Under WP7, T7.1 provides the guidelines for overall communication, engagement and dissemination activities to be performed during the project in the form of the Plan for

Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation of results (PCDE; D7.1). In addition, T7.2 (Outreach at European level) foresees social media communication campaigns designed for enhancing and aligning the public and civic engagement strategy (T7.2), while T7.4 (Networking and clustering activities) entails the mobilization, fostering the connection of ViSS with EU and international markets and players of the bio-based plastics value chain, the participation in external events, the organization of ViSS events at EU level, and cooperation with existing and future relevant European projects/initiatives. Moreover, the lessons learnt from the project and public engagement actions will enable to perform Open Innovation and Capacity Building activities (T7.5) and ease the post-project exploitation & long-term feasibility (T7.6).

ViSS Public Engagement strategy is committed to the IAP2 Core Values for Public Participation (IAP2, 2022) which will contribute to identifying those aspects of public participation which cross national, cultural, and religious boundaries, and help make better decisions which reflect the interests and concerns of potentially affected stakeholders:

1. Public participation is based on the belief that **those who are affected by a decision have a right to be involved in the decision-making process.**
2. Public participation includes the promise that **the public's contribution will influence the decision.**
3. Public participation promotes sustainable decisions by **recognising and communicating the needs and interests of all participants**, including decision-makers.
4. Public participation seeks out and facilitates the **involvement of those potentially affected by or interested in a decision.**
5. Public participation **seeks input from participants** in designing how they participate.
6. Public participation **provides participants with the information they need** to participate in a meaningful way.
7. Public participation **communicates** to participants **how their input affected the decision.**

The process of citizen engagement entails different levels of public participation based on the *Spectrum of Public Participation* (Figure 2). In ViSS project, the level of participation required will be analysed in subsequent sections, according to the goals of the specific action, its complexity and sensitivity.

Figure 2. IAP2 Spectrum of Public Participation

- Inform:** These actions are aimed at **providing the public with balanced and objective information** to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions. The Inform level is considered as transversal across the spectrum of processes since effective engagement requires a strategic flow of information. Examples: capacity building actions, packaging showcases in supermarkets, attendance to science weeks and other dissemination events.
- Consult:** These actions are aimed at **obtaining public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions, but with little interaction**. This level is appropriate when specific input is required by the public but early engagement is not possible. The targeted public is informed about how their feedback influenced the decision. Examples: interviews, surveys and questionnaires among partners and stakeholders on their needs and requirements, environmental awareness, packaged food consumption and recycling behaviours.
- Involve:** Actions at this level require **working with the public to ensure that concerns and needs are understood and considered**, by means of a two-way exchange of information and discussion and providing opportunities to influence the outcome. Decisions at this level are made by the administrations, although the issues raised should be considered. Examples: citizen science initiatives, focus groups and study circles.
- Collaborate:** Actions in which **the public is directly engaged in decision-making and involved in the interactive process**, often including an attempt to find consensus solutions. These actions require creating trust and ensuring a genuine engagement, being costly and time-consuming while implying risks that can damage future relationships with key stakeholders. In the ViSS framework, this level corresponds to the stakeholders participating in Delphi consensus, workshops and co-creation activities for the SSbD framework.
- Empower:** This level represents the **highest participation grade**, in which the public is given the opportunity to make decisions for themselves. A decision could be made by the community through a process that requires little interaction, such as a referendum or voting measure. The level promises to implement what you decide. There are no activities in ViSS at the empower level, but it is considered that the empowerment is reached through the involvement of stakeholders in decision-making, through the awareness-raising about the problem to be addressed (specifically,

generation of waste in the food and packaging sector). This includes capacity building at the individual and collective level on the importance and economic, social and environmental benefits of the circular economy and the generation of a favourable environment allowing the development of active and binding participation for the implantation of the ViSS model.

The selection of suitable resources and key actors from civil society, business and industry, research and education allow to benefit from synergies and avoid an overlapping of measures or citizens overburden.

The ViSS public engagement strategy will be deployed following a three-step process:

1. **Ecosystem analysis** (section 3): Gathering information on existing resources for public participation in the region of Murcia and the province of Alicante, both in terms of relevant infrastructure and stakeholders.
2. **Diagnosis** (section 4): In which the virtual and F2F infrastructures detected in the ecosystem analysis and suitable for the ViSS project are selected, drafting recommendations and analysing of the level of participation required in the action plan, to determine the infrastructures that must be designed.
3. **Action Plan** (section 5): Based on the ecosystem analysis and the diagnosis, this section is an action-oriented timeline in which key resources and responsibilities are defined together with concrete activities. The action plan is dynamic, and therefore developed in a collaborative way, revised and adjusted along the project lifecycle.
4. **Dissemination and Communication** (section 6) The actions to be delivered will be accompanied by dissemination and communication campaigns, aligned with the overall Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan (D7.1) planned at EU level.

3 Ecosystem analysis

This section aims to analyse the existing citizen engagement infrastructures and processes, to ensure the efficiency and effectiveness of the ViSS citizen engagement strategies in **the region of Murcia** and the **province of Alicante** (Community of Valencia), where the project takes place, as shown in Figure 3. Because of their differences and the different actors present, there will be differentiated actions. The use of these infrastructures in ViSS will be further explained in the section diagnosis, and action plan.

Figure 3. Regional scope of the engagement strategy

The region of Murcia and the province of Alicante (Valencian Community) are **NUTS3 regions** located in southeast Spain (Figure 3). They are limited in the north by the province Valencia (Valencian Community), Almeria (Andalusia) in the southwest, Granada and Jaen (Andalusia) in the west, and Albacete (Castilla La Mancha) on the northwest.

The region of Murcia is comprised by 45 municipalities, with a total population of 1,531,878 inhabitants (INE, 2023) mostly concentrated in the main cities: Murcia (head of the Region) and Cartagena. The main research centres (University of Murcia and Polytechnical University of Cartagena) as well as the public administration bodies and industry are concentrated around these two cities.

The province of Alicante is comprised by 141 municipalities, and a population of 1,974,438 people 2023. Alicante and Elche cities concentrate more than 25% of the population and the main universities

of the region (University of Alicante, University Miguel Hernández of Elche).

The activities developed under the engagement strategy and their results will be studied in terms of replicability and transferability to other regions and countries at the EU level, to be taken into consideration in Tasks 7.4 (Networking and Clustering) and 7.6 (Post-project exploitation & long-term feasibility).

3.1 Citizen Engagement Infrastructures

3.1.1 Murcia

3.1.1.1 Virtual Infrastructures

Virtual infrastructures comprise online platforms, application software, and collaborative channels having as a purpose citizen engagement at all levels (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower), in the region and its municipalities.

- **Fundación Séneca** (<https://fseneca.es/>). The Seneca Foundation-Agency for Science and Technology of the Region of Murcia is an entity belonging to the Regional Public Sector (depending from the Regional Ministry of Business, Employment, Universities and Spokesperson's Office). It was created in 1996 in order to contribute to the promotion and execution of scientific and technological research of excellence in all areas of knowledge, the transfer and application of the results of research activity and the social appreciation for science and technology. The Seneca Foundation promotes scientific and technological research, strengthening the links with industry, and offers. The website offers information on research advances, trends and funding opportunities, and the Foundation organizes the Science Week every year in Murcia in which different stakeholders (industry, research and technological centres, universities) disseminate their projects in an interactive way. The Agency also communicates through Twitter using the account [@FundacionSeneca](https://twitter.com/FundacionSeneca).
- **Region of Murcia Participation Platform** (<https://participa.carm.es/>). The Region of Murcia participation platform responds to the regulation document (Law 12/2014 of the Region of Murcia Autonomous Community) that recognises the rights of citizens to participate in public

affairs and requests the implementation of measures and tools to articulate this participation, applied within the scope of public administration of the Region of Murcia Autonomous Community and entities conforming the public sector. It is aimed at the Region's citizens as well as citizen organisations having the region as their main area of activity. This technological platform is managed by the CARM and specifically, by the Office for Transparency and Citizen Participation (OTPC). It allows the diffusion, and the management of the citizen participation tools, promoting channels to interact with regional administrations in designing and evaluating public policies. The website also includes links to different territorial scopes of participation, such as the municipalities, communities of citizens from Murcia in other Spanish regions and abroad, participation at the national and the EU level, as well as resources and information for associations. Other contents provide information on activities to promote citizen participation, such as workshops or funding. The platform also communicates through Twitter using the account @RMTransparencia.

3.1.1.2 Face to face infrastructures

In person participation structures include those in which people can physically see one another, in person (meetings in the same room) or virtually through teleconferences. Different types of collegiate bodies operate in the Region of Murcia, among which those related to the topics of ViSS will be described. These bodies meet the requirements of the government (President, Vice-president, or Regional Councillors):

- **Regional Environmental Advisory Council:** Comprised of representatives of the regional government, universities, research centres, environmental associations, consumer associations, business associations and commerce chambers. It should meet every quarter. According to news in the press, environmental organisations left the council in 2018 and later again in 2020, allegedly based on the lack of significance in decision-making¹.
- **Regional Advisory Council of Social Economy:** Includes representatives of the regional government, municipalities, social businesses, and labour unions.

In addition, the following bodies are technical and consultative boards that provide qualified advice on the issues considered by the President or Vice-President:

- **Regional Consumption Advisory Council:** Comprised of representatives of business associations, as well as consumers and users' associations, regional and local administrations.
- **Regional Advisory Council on Citizen Participation:** Includes representatives of the regional government, representatives of civic organisations and public servers in local and regional administrations. This council meets on a biannual basis (ordinary meetings) and as required by one-third of its members (extraordinary meetings).

3.1.2 Alicante

The Directorate-General for Citizen Participation carries out the functions established in terms of participation and associationism, coordination of the communication of its institutions with citizens, especially through social networks and other technological means² as well as the promotion of education in participation and associations. It is also responsible for coordinating the Council's

¹ <https://www.murcia.com/region/noticias/2018/11/06-manifiesta-inutilidad-consejo-asesor-de-medio-ambiente.asp>

² Comunidad Valenciana, Ley 5/1983, de 30 de diciembre, de Gobierno Valenciano, vol. BOE-A-1984-3460. 1984, pp. 3457–3462. Accessed: Jan. 29, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.boe.es/eli/es-vc/l/1983/12/30/5>

policies on citizen participation and is responsible for institutional relations with groups of Valencian people living outside the Community, with civic entities that bring together Valencian citizens residing abroad and with regional houses and federations of associations from other autonomous communities in the Valencian Community. Moreover, the General Directorate for Public Engagement coordinates the policies for public participation through the design and implementation of corresponding guidelines (Generalitat Valenciana, 2011) and manages the registry of associations at the regional level.

The guidelines for public participation establish the procedures and channels for public participation and the bodies and instruments for participation in the Valencian Community. Among them, those that are relevant for ViSS project are described in this document.

3.1.2.1 *Community of Valencia Participation Platform*

The online participative processes in the province of Alicante are guaranteed by the Law 4/2023 of the Region of Valencia Autonomous Community. The platform GVA Participa (<https://gvaparticipa.gva.es/>), managed by the Community of Valencia, is the regional tool to facilitate the online participation of citizens and it is the main tool to interact with regional administrations in designing and evaluating public policies. To make contributions to the platform it is mandatory to set a user and login. The platform hosts four main participative processes: facilitate Discussion, propose and support Initiatives, comment on proposed regional Legislation and Collaborative Budgets:

- **Discussion:** the platform gives the opportunity for citizens or organizations to propose ideas. These ideas (for instance: promotion of physical activity and sport or is it possible to regulate the civic management of some public services?) can be commented by other users and it can be 'liked' or 'disliked'.
- **Initiatives:** in a similar way to Discussion, the users of the platform can propose more tangible initiatives or project that could have more direct response from the Administration (for instance: Creation of optic-optometrist places in public health or Rehabilitation of the House of Tristán in Segorbe).
- **Collaborative legislation – Public consultation:** This option allows the collection of opinions from the citizens about specific actions or initiatives of the regional government. Users can therefore collaborate in the drafting and modification of regulations or plans and programs of the Region.
- **Collaborative budgets:** It aims to be a participatory process to decide the actions to which a part of the Region's budget is dedicated. It is a relevant tool to move towards an open government that revolves around citizen participation.

3.1.2.2 *Face to face infrastructures*

Different types of collegiate bodies operate in the Province of Alicante, among which those related to the topics of ViSS will be described. These bodies meet as required by the government (President, Vice-president, or Regional Councillors):

- **Regional Citizen Participation Council:** The Participation Council is the advisory body and channel for the participation of public and private institutions and entities, with the functions, composition and procedure established in Decree 190/2016 of the Valencian Community, among them contributing to the guidelines of public participation. The council is comprised by 31 representatives of the Public Administrations and Universities, and 31 representatives of citizens

and expert persons (Generalitat Valenciana, 2020), elected every 3 years. It works in plenary sessions and through working groups on different topics.

- **Regional Advisory and Participatory Council in Environment (CAPMA).** Represents the participatory body of social and professional organisations for environmental and quality of life issues. It is composed by 25 members from the public administrations and universities, and 4 members of entrepreneurial or professional associations. Later, the Council expanded to include more environmental associations (4) and other entities that organise activities in the environment (i.e. sports). The CAPMA informs on action programmes of the Candelaria with environmental competencies and participates in awareness-raising campaigns on environmental topics.
- **Regional Council of Consumers and Users.** It is the consultive and advisory body representing consumers and users in the Generalitat. Composed by 6 representatives from the administrations and 15 representatives of the citizens and is devoted to monitoring and assessing consumer protection systems and to proposing normatives to protect the interest of citizens.

3.1.2.3 Local Level: City of Alicante

The city Hall of Alicante develops functions related to associations, neighbourhood activities and coordination of districts through the Department of Public Participation. This department owns the Centre for Associations and Volunteering as a space for communication and co-working among organisations and citizenship and implements programmes for awareness raising and training. It also provides spaces for volunteering entities to perform their activities. The interest in ViSS lies on the generation of networks and the cooperation in awareness raising activities regarding circular economy.

Moreover, it is worth highlighting the Environment Department of the City Hall and the activities performed aimed at raising awareness on ecological footprint, recycling, ocean pollution among others, that may generate synergies with VISS projects through the organization of seminars, contests and citizen science activities.

In addition, the University of Alicante organizes since 2018 the MSCA Researchers' Night (September) aimed at secondary schools and vocational training centres, as well as general public, in which a variety of activities are organised, among them related to circular economy such as the presence of microplastics in our environments. This activity represents an opportunity to engage general society in awareness raising activities such as the described in the Diagnosis (section 4.1) and the Action Plan (section 5).

4 Diagnosis

After the analysis of the existing virtual and face-to-face infrastructures in the previous section, the following have been selected as they are relevant to the scope of the ViSS project and topics (Circular Economy, Environmental Management). **Participation will be promoted through information about ViSS activities and results, and promoting consultations and activities related to circular economy such as surveys, talks, and encouraging public debate on the topics of the project.**

Table 1. Virtual and face-to-face infrastructures for participation at regional and local level

Type	Murcia	Alicante
Virtual	Fundación Seneca Region of Murcia Participation Platform	Community of Valencia Participation Platform
Face-to-face	Murcia Science Week Regional Environmental Assessment Council	Regional Advisory and Participatory Council in Environment (CAPMA) University of Alicante Researchers' Night

Moreover, **key alliances** are being identified based on the analysis of the key stakeholders. Questionnaires will be used along the project implementation aimed at the different stakeholders to visualise the degree of affinity with the project objectives and their capacity to influence in this context.

A preliminary analysis based on previous related projects has resulted in the development of a SWOT matrix (Figure below) for engagement processes in the field of bioplastics and circular economy.

Figure 4. Preliminary SWOT matrix: engagement processes for the implantation of the circular economy

The **detected strengths and opportunities should be considered alongside the ViSS project** to consolidate the strategy and to foster the adoption of the solutions and results proposed in other EU contexts.

4.1 Levels of Participation in ViSS Activities

VISS foresees engagement processes through activities carried out in the Region of **Murcia** and the province of **Alicante**, as well as at EU level, that entail different levels of participation, based on the *Spectrum of Public Participation* (see Figure 2).

The spectrum ranges from low participation, where people are simply informed about the relevant problems and alternative solutions (on websites for example) to high participation, where they are empowered to take the final decision on the issue at hand (i.e., through deliberative forums or referendums)(Ostling et al., 2016).

The spectrum levels within the VISS project will be applied as follows:

Citizen engagement goal: To provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions.

Promise to the public: We will keep you informed.

Information only involves a one-way flow of information from the project to citizens, although it is an important foundation for community engagement since it builds knowledge and allows citizens to understand the public decision-making process and take informed decisions. The Inform level of public participation gives citizens what they need to fully understand the project's actions so that they can reach their own conclusions. Some authors (Chappell, 2016; Susskind and Carson, 2008). consider that the Inform level should be placed across the spectrum, since effective engagement requires effective information. This way, although informing does not involve community participation per se (City of Newcastle, 2013), it increases the understanding of the issues, the ability of the stakeholders and communities to address them, and the compliance with regulations (Department of Environment, Land, Water and Planning, 2015).

The Inform level is appropriate in **situations where there is no opportunity for the public to influence decision-making and simply informing them is the appropriate activity**. Indeed, all the relevant stakeholders (administration, business, academia, and civic society) will be targeted at the Inform level on all the activities and results of the ViSS project through the project website (<https://viss-project.eu/>), social media (@ViSS_project in Twitter/X and [LinkedIn](#)), scientific dissemination, press releases, flyers and brochures. These activities are further described in D7.1 and will require coordination between the related tasks. Some examples of activities are:

- i) Third parties' events such as the Science Week Fair organised by Fundación Seneca, held every year at the end of October/beginning of November at the Malecon Park (Murcia) where technological parks (CETEC) have a dedicated stand, will constitute an opportunity to engage users through posters and small experiments or merchandise related to the project to general society (families, schools), policy-makers and industry. AGROFOOD also collaborates in this event. In the case of Alicante, UA participates in the Science Week organised by the Alicante City Council and the MSCA Researcher's Night at UA Campus
 - (i) Awareness raising talks will happen in primary/secondary schools, VET centres, universities, and industry actors.
 - (ii) Training activities (included in T7.5) aim to train professionals (active and potential), unemployed people as lifelong training, universities and cover not only technical and technological aspects, but also the financial and perspectives (especially for companies).
 - (iii) Scientific and professional dissemination, as further described D7.1.

- (iv) Industry fairs and events: It is also planned to participate in events such as fairs, symposiums, and brokerage events in different sectors.

Citizen engagement goal: To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions.

Promise to the public: We will keep you informed and will acknowledge concerns and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.

The Consult level of public participation focuses on feedback and is the minimum opportunity for the public to input on analysis, alternatives, or decisions. The responsibility for the decisions remains with the government or the organisations doing the consulting (i.e., the project manager).

The Consult level is appropriate when specific input is sought from citizens for the decision-making, but early engagement is not possible throughout the process. There is a wide range of ways to perform consultations, some of which include processes that require little or no dialogue (surveys in a newsletter or digital platform) or involve a debate (public meetings, focus groups).

Within VISS, **different surveys and questionnaires will be used aimed at civil society**, but also to **entrepreneurs and companies**, framed in the evaluation of the social impact evaluation and improvement of the social readiness of the delivered solutions (WP6). The surveys would be tailored depending on the sector/group, using quantitative and qualitative methods.

- i) In the case of civil society, the surveys or questionnaires will cover their perception on the importance of environmental impacts, as well as their consumption and disposal habits of sweets and plastic packages.

In the case of companies and entrepreneurs, the questionnaires will be aimed at improving the effectivity of VISS solutions, while reducing the cost of implementation.

The collaboration of partners will be asked to obtain results, through links in their websites. Also, the EU Platform EU Survey (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/>) will also constitute a useful tool for consultations.

Citizen engagement goal: To work with the public to make sure that concerns and aspirations are considered and understood.

Promise to the public: we will work with you to ensure that your concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the alternatives developed and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.

At the Involve level, citizens are invited into the process to a greater extent than at the Consult level. The goal is to work with the public throughout the process and to make use of their knowledge and expertise on a given issue. This implies a two-way exchange of information that encourages discussion while providing an opportunity to influence the outcome. The Involve level not only ensures a common understanding, but also the products or services provided are better tailored to

the stakeholders' needs. The regulation, standardisation or behaviour needs are accepted and sustainable and the resources are effectively applied at this level.

At the Involve level, the public is invited into the process, usually from the beginning, and is provided multiple opportunities for input as decision-making progresses. However, while 'Involve' assumes a greater level of participation by stakeholders as they work through issues and alternatives to assist in the decision-making process, the organisation undertaking the engagement generally retains responsibility for the final decision. **In VISS, some of the activities at the involvement level are:**

- (i) **Citizen science activities**
- (ii) **Contests for young people**
- (iii) **Delphi groups**

Other activities included at this level are, i.e., workshops, focus groups on innovative business schemes and social sustainability indicators. These activities will be carried out in collaboration with other partners, such as IDE and TCA (see section 5.3), contributing to create a stakeholder community around the project as further described in D7.1 (section related to networking).

Citizen engagement goal: To partner with the public in each aspect of the decision-making.

Promise to the public: We will seek direct advice and innovation in formulating solutions from you. Your advice and recommendations will be incorporated into the decisions to the maximum extent possible.

At the Collaborate level, the public is directly engaged in decision-making in an interactive process with an emphasis on two-way processes. The Collaborate level of public engagement includes all the elements of Involve but takes it a step further, including an explicit attempt to find consensus solutions. However, similar to the Involve level of participation, the administration or project management board remains the ultimate decision-maker. The Collaborate level is particularly useful for controversial issues and complex problems because it entails a high level of participation.

In VISS the Collaborate level takes place within the consortium. On the one hand, the co-creation of the SSbD framework (including the indicators, and methodologies); furthermore, collaboration is needed to assess benefits, costs and feasibility and comparing the results with alternatives already in the market. Partners will provide data along the project implementation. In addition, the partners, led by ICONS and KVC, will collaborate in the development of business cases and the VISS Circular Business model.

Moreover, the collaboration will be sought with other projects funded under the same call (REBIOLUTION, <https://rebiolution-project.eu/>) or other related calls, for which a mapping will be performed, and the list updated along the project.

During the project implementation, **new stakeholders and projects will be contacted to join the stakeholders' network of VISS**, using mailing rounds, through the EU Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, the participation in Green Deal Working Groups, the SSbD network and other relevant organisations in discussions during significant events (i.e. Green Week) and they will be invited to join one project meeting per year where possible, in addition to other specific meetings.

4.2 ViSS Participation Infrastructure

In addition to the already existing participation infrastructures mentioned in section 3.1, the following virtual channels and sites will be used for the VISS public engagement:

- **Web platform:** ViSS website (<https://viss-project.eu/>) – active, managed by ICONS as WP7 leader. The website homepage includes information on the project, resources to download (deliverables, flyer, postcard), and news at EU level.
- **Social networks:** The Twitter/X channel (@ViSS_project), which was finally discontinued the 2nd of July 2024, and the [LinkedIn](#) profile have been set. Other social networks may be used if relevant, according to the dissemination and communication strategy (D7.1).

Figure 5. ViSS landing page in English

5 Action Plan

According to the diagnosis, the following engagement activities are planned within ViSS under the different levels of Engagement. In this section, a preliminary list of activities suitable for each level of participation is proposed. Nevertheless, it must be taken into consideration that **the action plan is dynamic, and it will be updated in a collaborative manner**, with contributions from all partners.

5.1 Inform

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3				Year 4			
	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024	Q4 2024	Q1 2025	Q2 2025	Q3 2025	Q4 2025	Q1 2026	Q2 2026	Q3 2026	Q4 2026	Q1 2027	Q2 2027	Q3 2027
Short video clips				■	■			■	■				■		■	■
Talks					■	■		■	■	■		■	■	■		
Packaging showcases															■	■
Capacity building actions					■	■	■		■	■	■		■	■	■	
Events				■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	

Figure 6. Engagement activities at Inform Level

A wide variety of activities under the Inform level are planned in VISS (Figure 6):

- **Short video clips**, VISS project will produce tailored key messages delivered through dedicated easy-to-access and inclusive communication means. This includes the production of audiovisual productions. The objective is to produce more than four short videos and one project video with main results.
- **Talks to youngsters** More than 10 talks to youngsters will be delivered, aimed at raising awareness on circular economy and bioplastics. The talks will be eased by alliances with educational centres (primary and secondary schools, VET centres) and CSOs (youth associations, environmental associations).
- **Packaging showcases**. More than four packaging showcases for consumers in supermarkets and candy shops will be done to increase awareness among consumers. This activity strongly depends on the technical developments of the PHBV packaging and will take place at the end of the project. The project will leverage on special occasions (Environment Day, New Years' Day, World Recycling Day) to draw attention of the consumers through booths installed in the supermarkets with graphic arrangements and spreading messages with social content on the topics of the project.
- **Participation in external events**: This activity is framed in the overall dissemination (T7.4), Partners will take part on events such as the Science Week Fair organised by Seneca Foundation in Murcia (held every year at the end of October/beginning of November), or Researchers' Night (organised by UA) raising awareness on the challenges of plastic pollution and bioplastic solutions. Also, industry fairs and other events are foreseen along the project.
- **Capacity building actions**: Activity T7.5 will involve more than 40 capacity building actions (workshops, technical seminaries, etc) aimed at different sectors on different topics related to VISS:
 - a. **For industry**: recommendations for SSbD biobased plastics, bioplastics, the evaluation & decision tool and VISS PHBV replication study, VISS Circular Business Model and VISS entrepreneurship to foster social innovation; and the traceability tool, sorting protocols and end of life scenarios.

- b. For policy and decision makers: Policy briefs and recommendations on how to foster social readiness& marketability of bio-based plastics and how to communicate to consumers the disposal routes.
- c. For CSOs and decision makers: disseminating the public tool aimed at empowering consumers to make informed choices and fight disinformation.
- d. For the research community, sectorial groups and decision makers: SSbD & Social Readiness evaluation methodology.

5.2 Consult

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3				Year 4			
	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024	Q4 2024	Q1 2025	Q2 2025	Q3 2025	Q4 2025	Q1 2026	Q2 2026	Q3 2026	Q4 2026	Q1 2027	Q2 2027	Q3 2027
<u>Surveys, questionnaires</u>																

Figure 7 Action Plan for consultation activities

Consultation activities are foreseen in several activities of the project, through surveys and questionnaires (Figure 7):

- In Task 6.4.3, the analysis of socio-economic and enabling factors will include surveys and questionnaires, both existing such as the New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) (Dunlap et al., 2000) or developed ad hoc for the project, contributing to offer comprehensive insights on social structures and roles, environmental awareness and acceptability of bio-based products.
- In T7.6 post-project exploitation & long-term feasibility, ICONS will perform surveys and interviews among partners and stakeholders to explore socio-economic context, markets and users' needs.

5.3 Involve

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3				Year 4			
	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024	Q4 2024	Q1 2025	Q2 2025	Q3 2025	Q4 2025	Q1 2026	Q2 2026	Q3 2026	Q4 2026	Q1 2027	Q2 2027	Q3 2027
<u>Citizen science initiatives</u>																
<u>Contests and prizes</u>																
<u>Delphi groups for SSbD</u>																

Figure 8 Engagement activities at Involve level.

3 types of engagement activities are planned within the Involve level of ViSS (Figure 8):

- **Citizen science actions (UA).** In ViSS, citizen-science actions will involve at least 8 beach cleaning activities. To this end, UA will leverage on their Vice-rectorate on Equality, Inclusion and Social Responsibility and the Vice-rectorate of Research and Knowledge Transference; moreover, the activity will serve to stablish alliances with environmental associations committed to circular economy and reduction of oceans’ pollution. Citizen science activities will be planned in the first and third quarter of each year, to ensure the maximal outreach, and the data produced in these actions will be uploaded to Marine Litter Watch from EU environment Agency).
- **Contests and prizes (KVC).** More than six contests and will be organized, aimed at consumers and general public, related to solving problems related to circularity and end-of-life routes of bio-based plastics, to foster the sustainable attitudes and behaviours and to increase the acceptance of the biobased products. For these activities regional schools and high schools will be contacted, as well as CSOs such as consumers and neighbour associations. The contests and prizes can be held coordinated with other activities (such as the participation in citizen science actions) and coinciding with relevant dates for environmental protection (Oceans’ Day, Environment’s Day, Recycling Date, etc)
- **Delphi group for SSbD.** A 2-round Delphi process will be performed to contribute to the definition of the SSbD framework (T6.2), for which an external expert group will be set up. The expert group will be conformed based on the networks of the partners, but also leveraging on existing platforms of experts in the SSbD methodology such as the created by the European Commission on SSbD, with the areas of knowledge described in Table 2.

Table 2. Expertise of the expert group

Safety-risk assessment	Environmental & sustainability impact
Social impact.	Circular bioeconomy
Consumers’ representative.	Decision making.
Recyclers’ representative.	Industrial end-users’ representatives.

The Delphi process will imply the definition of 2 groups:

- Group 1 focused on safety, environmental & economic sustainability of bio-based plastics (led by IDE)
- Group 2 focused on social readiness for bio-based plastics (led by KVC)

A workshop with these external experts will take place on Q3 of 2024 (end April/beginning of May). Moreover, the expert group will support the innovation and co-creation processes across the ViSS transdisciplinary actions, and the monitoring and evaluation of ViSS results through nonbiased views, in face to face and online events.

5.4 Collaborate

As indicated in section 4.1, the collaboration level in ViSS takes place mainly within the consortium. The following activities are foreseen (Figure 9).

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3				Year 4			
	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024	Q4 2024	Q1 2025	Q2 2025	Q3 2025	Q4 2025	Q1 2026	Q2 2026	Q3 2026	Q4 2026	Q1 2027	Q2 2027	Q3 2027
SsbD approach: workshops, co-creation and assessment activities																
Roundtables and meetings																
Cross-fertilisation activities																

Figure 9. Engagement activities at Collaboration level

- **SSbD approach, workshops, co-creation and assessment activities.** The definition of the SSbD framework (D6.3), as well as the monitoring and evaluation of the results considering environmental, economic and social dimensions, will be performed through co-creation workshops.
- **Development of SSbD approach (T6.2).** Partners will be divided according to their expertise, to define the methodologies and indicators in two different groups that will collaborate with the external experts described in section 5.3:
 - safety, environmental & economic sustainability of bio-based plastics (IDE, UA, VTT, CETEC, TCA, KVC)
 - social readiness of biobased plastics (KVC, ICONS, TCA)

The first workshop for the definition of the SSbD framework will be organised in March 2024 (coinciding with the General Assembly); the results will be validated with the external experts on the mentioned workshop (end April 2024).

Monitoring and evaluation will be carried out, assessing the baseline (approx. Q4 2024) until the final evaluation (2027).

Along the project, more than 15 workshops and co-creation activities will be held:

- Group 1 by KVC for the social readiness assessment involving consumers, decision makers, industry and research communities by KVC.
 - Group 2 by IRIS, CETEC & AITEX with industrial/recycling sectors and decision makers in charge of waste management schemes aimed to gaining common insights in further management schemes for biodegradable plastic products, including their sorting.
- **Round tables and meetings (KVC, IDE):** will be aimed at supporting the implementation of ViSS CEBM (with financial intermediaries) and supporting SSbD and social readiness for bio-based value-chains (decision makers, CSOs, industries).
 - **Cross-fertilisation activities** with initiatives and projects, will be closely related to task 7.4 on networking and clustering. Some examples of initiatives are those related to residues as feedstocks for biotechnological processes, SSbD approach, social readiness for plastic products, bio-based plastics, recycling & sorting, and governance models for the waste management of bio-based value chains. Cooperation with initiatives including the Knowledge Centre on Bioeconomy (KCB), Joint Research Centre (JRC) will be sought for sharing methodologies and enabling common approaches. The objectives at this level are

referred to the creation and animation of a **Stakeholder Community**. Further information on the methods can be found in D7.1. (Networking and clustering section).

5.5 Empower

The Empower level has the objective of *placing final decision-making in the hands of the public, requiring the development of stable participation, monitoring and evaluation structures that have competencies and decision-making capacity*. There are no activities in ViSS that directly address the empower level. On the other hand, it is considered that the empower level is reached through the involvement in the decision making and policies processes. This entails 3 conditions:

- An enhanced awareness about the circular economy, the territory and the sectors involved.
- The deployment of capacity building mechanisms at the individual and collective level.
- The generation of a favourable environment allowing the development of an active and binding participation.

Therefore, **the ViSS Public Tool embedded in the ICT platform developed (D6.1) and nurtured with data (D6.4 and D6.4) by CETEC can be considered as an empowerment activity**, as it will enable the capture and communicate reliable information about the ViSS value chain and its impacts, thus empowering consumers to make informed choices and fight disinformation and “greenwashing”. The public tool is not only aimed at citizens and consumers, but also to CSOs and decision makers, supporting the inclusion of the project outcomes in regulations and the implementation of policies related to plastic packaging and waste management.

Moreover, the Capacity building actions (see Inform level, section 5.1) will contribute to the social readiness and the adoption of circular economy results.

6 Dissemination and Communication

Dissemination and Communication activities are further detailed in D7.1 (Preliminary Plan of Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation) and will be revised and updated according to the results in the reports on Dissemination and Communication (D7.8) and Public Engagement activities (D7.4) to ensure the achievement of the project objectives.

During the time since the beginning of the project (October 2023) and the publication of this document (February 2024), the project has been disseminated through the main website and social media. Furthermore, dissemination and communication materials in Spanish with a stronger focus on the activities carried out at the local level (citizen science activities, showcases in supermarkets, talks and contests) will be elaborated with catchy messages tailored to the different stakeholders and levels of engagement in ViSS project.

The dissemination and communication activities in Murcia and Alicante will allow the sharing of data and the collection of information relevant for these objectives, putting special attention to multiplier agent (civil society entities, NGOs, foundations, cultural centres, industrial clusters, etc.) The most important objective (primary objective) is to engage the relevant local stakeholders to participate in the SRL assessment, to enhance the acceptability of VISS results, which implies to support the required social changes. The Dissemination and communication should also consider

research on the position of different stakeholders (unravelling affinities or opposition groups), specific audience targeting, and continuous adjustment of the messages provided, when required, linked to the follow-up of the actions and responses obtained (including audiences' reactions and unintended results) for which the Engagement strategy and the Dissemination and Communication activities will be revised and updated along the project according to the general guidelines provided by ICONS (WP leader).

6.1 Approach

A double approach (upstream and downstream) will be used in VISS dissemination and communication for engagement:

- **Upstream:** refers to reaching a group that has interpersonal influence and can create change due to its relationship with the service-users instead of directly targeting the service-users (for example, citizens, companies, entrepreneurs or professionals of waste management or food industry). In addition, these groups could be more likely to influence and have the ability to modify contextual factors. For instance, policy-makers, public administration officers, community leaders or investors are groups to be considered in upstream actions.

- **Downstream:** to recruit service users for the VISS will involve a significant effort in social marketing and public communication. Efforts should be made to design and implement the campaigns responding to the specific needs and preferences of citizens and main sub-targets.

It must be taken into consideration that upstream initiatives might be necessary for downstream efforts to be effective.

6.2 Target Audience and Media

Citizen engagement and communication campaigns, even when they appear to address the general public, are directed toward specific segments of the population as seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Target groups aligned with the Quintuple Helix of Innovation

VISS campaigns for engagement will be promoted through the media and official channels mentioned in D7.1 (platforms, online social media, mass media, interpersonal channels, small group meetings, etc). The media of choice will depend on the key message and specific audiences for each communication campaign, as shown in Table 9.

The campaigns will be carried out in Spanish and Valencian languages to ensure the understanding with the local communities.

6.3 Communication Campaigns

VISS Communication Campaigns (CC) are shown in the following table 3.

Table 3. Communication campaigns (CC) for public engagement

ID (CC: Communication Campaign)	Aim	Target group	Key message	Approach	Channels	Resources
INFORM						
CC1.1	To inform stakeholders about the VISS project.	Society as a whole, CSOs	<i>VISS will develop and test bioplastic-based packaging</i>	Downstream	Local press/TV/radio Social media Local website	Current media presence. Flyer Posters
CC1.2	To disseminate the concept and results		<i>That's how VISS works. We'll keep you up to date!</i>	Downstream	Website Social media Local press, TV or radio Knowledge transfer and training	Personal networks and relations with Media Events (i.e., Science Week, showcasing events)
CC1.3	To share knowledge on VISS products and processes	Research and education Decision makers, Industry	<i>Learn new pathways to circularity! Take your region/community/company a step forward in sustainability.</i>	Upstream and downstream	Training and knowledge transfer Policy briefs/recommendations	Conferences Events Capacity building activities VISS Public tool
CONSULT						
CC2.1	To obtain valuable information and feedback	Citizens, service users (entrepreneurs, professionals, waste managers, plastic producers, food producers)	<i>Without you, VISS does not make sense. Let us know your opinion! We want to hear your voice: Tell us about your perception of bioplastic packaging</i>	Downstream	Website Social media Local press, TV or radio	Partner's platforms (links) Social media Local press, TV or radio Media presence. Tools for feedback gathering (surveys,

ID (CC: Communication Campaign)	Aim	Target group	Key message	Approach	Channels	Resources
						questionnaires on EU survey.
INVOLVE						
CC3.1		Citizens, educational centres, NGOs	<i>What types of plastic end in the environment? Come and do your bit discovering and sharing data. Take part in our event [substitute by the name of the event in each case]</i>	Downstream	Social media Website Local press/TV/radio	Current media presence. Personal networks and relations with media and multipliers
CC3.2	To recruit youth people in talks and contests	Civil society, youth associations, educational schools	<i>Plastic packages are not waste but treasure. Participate in our talks to learn more! Bring your circular ideas and get an award! Take part in our contest [name of the event in each case]</i>	Downstream		
CC3.3	To recruit experts for co-creating the SSbD framework	Consumers, recyclers, industrial end users' representatives, Investors, researchers, policy makers	<i>The production of safe and sustainable plastics for packaging must consider health, environmental and social aspects to become a success. Participate in VISS contributing to decide on the most significant factors [name of the event in each case]</i>	Upstream	Partners' networks (direct engagement) Website	
COLLABORATE						

ID (CC: Communication Campaign)	Aim	Target group	Key message	Approach	Channels	Resources
CC4	To support the implementation of VISS business models and supporting social readiness	Partners Other projects in the call/similar calls	<i>Collaborate with us fostering bio-based value chains!</i> <i>Participate in our event</i>	Downstream	Personal networks Events (Webinars, roundtables) Press/TV/radio Social media Website	Current media presence Flyers Presentations Personal networks and relations with media
EMPOWER						
CC5	To raise loyalty and engagement during the pilot implementation	Service-users (i.e., poultry industry, waste management, sweet industry and vendors, plastic packaging producers, citizens people participating and already involved)	Register in our public tool to keep track of VISS recycling routes Make a step forward circularity! Keep informed about circular economy and engage with your community	Downstream	VISS Public Tool Capacity building Awareness raising Policy recommendations	Current media presence Webinars Presentations Personal networks and relations with media

7 Conclusions

The objectives of public engagement in VISS are:

- to **involve the relevant stakeholders** for participating in the SRL assessment to be carried out in WP6 (T6.4),
- to **enhance the acceptability** of ViSS results and solutions,
- to **support the social change** processes and increasing awareness,
- to **support communication & dissemination** activities.
-

The Deliverable 7.3 Public Engagement Strategy of the VISS will require continuous revision and updating, particularly the calendar of activities in the action plan, and the dissemination and communication section to ensure the foreseen objectives and goals allowing the long-term sustainability of VISS results. The impact of engagement activities will be assessed in D7.4 (M18), D7.8 (M24) and D7.15 (48). The effectiveness of Communication and dissemination activities (linked to the inform level) will be assessed in D7.3 (M18) and D7.14 (M48).

The activities in the engagement activity will be focused to the regional level (Murcia and Alicante) where there is a variety of stakeholders and participation infrastructures to engage society at different levels (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower).

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9 Annex I. Stakeholders

9.1 Public administration

Table 4 Public administration sector stakeholders at the regional level

MURCIA	ALICANTE
Regional Government	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consejería de Educación, Formación Profesional y Empleo • Consejería de Economía, Hacienda y Empresa • Consejería de Presidencia, Portavocía y Acción Exterior (Oficina de la Transparencia y la Participación Ciudadana de la Administración Pública de la Región de Murcia) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conselleria de Innovación, Industria, Comercio y Turismo • Conselleria de Educación, Universidades y Empleo • Dirección General de Participación Ciudadana
Public services	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Murcia Regional Development Agency (INFO) • Scientific Park in Murcia (depending on INFO, hosts technological businesses) • Official Commerce Chambers (Murcia, Cartagena, Lorca) • Fundación Séneca (Science and Technology Agency) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific Park Alicante (depending of UA) • Office commerce Chambers (Alicante and Orihuela) • Valencian Agency for Innovation • AIMPLAS (Plastic Technological Institute)

9.2 Private sector

Table 5 Private sector stakeholders at the regional level

MURCIA	ALICANTE
Private Organisations and Industry	
<p>Plastic converters and recyclers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eversia • Palec Ecológico • Galian Plasticos • Onlyplast Spain • Walki Plasbel • Reciclajes Plásticos • Plastirama • Plasticos Ros Marin • Green World Compounding • Industrias Anfra • Solplast • Puromaster • Servicios Plásticos • Polimur • Cristobal Meseguer • Manufacturas Adelplast 	<p>Plastic converters and recyclers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indesla Packaging • Viduca • Termoformados Banyeres • ITC Packaging • Termoformas • Totemplast • GreatPlastic • Juypal Hogar • Plasticol • Sarabia Pack • Plásticos Jijona • Plasticos Francés • <u>Vicedo</u> Martí • Acteco • BSDI • Suinso

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jokey Ibérica 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telas minido • Pérez Linares Plastic Solutions • Plásticos Inden • Prepi • Plásticos Acrílicos Alicante
Food/confectionary producers	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vidal golosinas • Fini golosinas • Caramelos Celdrán • Zukan • Jake 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interdulces
Retailers, Supermarkets, Services	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food chains (Aldi, Mercadona, Lidl, Spar, Superdumbo, Vidal, Más y Más) • SMEs, entrepreneurs (small supermarkets, market vendors, local shops) 	
Agrifood Clusters and Associations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agritech Murcia • Fundación Cluster Agroalimentario de la Región de Murcia • Proexport- Asociación de Productores-Exportadores de Frutas y Hortalizas de la Región de Murcia • Fecoam-Federación de Cooperativas Agrarias de Murcia (FECOAM) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FEDACOVA (Federación Empresarial de Agroalimentación de la Comunidad Valenciana)
Industrial and Business Associations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asemuplast (Region of Murcia) • AMIQ (Association of Chemical Industries in the Region of Murcia) • AEMA RM (Environmental Businesses Association-Region of Murcia) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AVEP (Valencian Association of Plastic Entrepreneurs) • APPA (Association of Plastics in Alicante) • Quimacova (Chemical and Environmental Association of the Chemical sector in Valencian Community) • ANEPMA (Association of Public enterprises in Alicante for environmental management) • CE/R+S- Club of Responsible and Sustainable Enterprises of the Valencian Community
Financing Intermediaries	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caja Rural Central • Caja Rural Regional 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Banco Sabadell • La Caixa • Caixa Ontinyent
Private Non-Profit Organisations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CETENMA- Technological Centre for Energy and Environment • CEEIM- Business and Technological Centre in Murcia • CEEIC- Business and Technological Centre in Cartagena 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Textile Industry Research Association – AITEX • European Centre of Business and Innovation- Elche • European Centre of Business and Innovation- Alcoy

9.3 Civil society

Table 6 Civil society organisations related to ViSS at regional level.

MURCIA	ALICANTE
Environmental Associations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambiente Europeo • Región de Murcia Limpia • Murcia Residuo Cero • Teachers for future, Fridays for future, parents for future • Ecologistas en Acción Región de Murcia • ANSE- Asociación de Naturalistas del Sureste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bioagradables • Alicante Renace • Ecologistas en Acción Comunidad Valenciana
Education Associations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confederación Regional De Asociaciones De Madres Y Padres De Alumnos De Murcia "CONFAMUR" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FAPAALicante (Federation of Students parents associations in Alicante)
Consumer Organisations (and others)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federación murciana de asociaciones de amas de casa, consumidores y usuarios THADER • Asociación de Consumidores y Usuarios en Red, CONSUMUR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACA Association of Consumers Alicante • ADACUA (Association of consumers and users Alicante) • Consumo2000
Professional Associations and Trade Unions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmentalists Official College (COAMBRM) • Chemists Official College (COLQUIMUR) • Biologists Official College • Biotechnologists Association Region of Murcia (BIOTECMUR) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COAMBCV – Official College Environmentalists Community of Valencia • COIQCV- Official College Chemical Engineers Community of Valencia • ColegioQuimicosCV - Official College Chemistry Community of Valencia • COBCV- Official College Biologists Community of Valencia

9.4 Research and education.

Table 7. Education and research entities at the regional level

MURCIA	ALICANTE
UM (University of Murcia)	University of Alicante (UA)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University Institute of Water and Environment (INUAMA) • Chair on Water and sustainability - EMUASA • Chair on Food security and sustainability • Open Chair for innovation and participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University Institute for Materials • University Institute for the Engineering of Chemical Processes • Chemical Engineering Department • Department Of Biochemistry And Molecular Biology And Soil And Agricultural Chemistry • Chemical Processes Engineering Institute

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Department of Organic Chemistry
Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena (UPCT)	Universidad Miguel Hernandez (UMH)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mechanical engineering, materials, and manufacturing Department Environmental and Chemical Engineering Institute of Plant Biotechnology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific Park UMH Bioengineering Research Institute Agrochemistry and Environment Department
Universidad Católica San Antonio (UCAM)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chair on Food for Health Chair on Sustainable Development Chair on Circular Economy and SCR Chair on biomaterial engineering Chair on Responsible Agrofood Systems Chair on Insect industrial production and Circular Economy in Biowaste management 	
UM & UPCT	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chair on Environment Autoridad Portuaria de Cartagena Campus Mare Nostrum 	
Research Centres	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CEBAS- CSIC- Soil Science and Applied Biology Centre IMIDA – Region of Murcia Institute for Research and Agricultural and Environmental Development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ramon Margalef Environmental Sciences Research Institute